

Social-Adaptive Functioning Evaluation (SAFE) study observations.

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Introduction

Adaptive behaviour is defined as behaviour that allows a person (usually a child) to cope in their environment with the greatest success and the least conflict with others. This is a phrase used in psychology and special education. Adaptive behaviour, like the term life skills, refers to everyday skills or tasks that the "average" person can complete.

Nonconstructive or disruptive social or personal behaviours can be used to achieve a constructive outcome in some cases. A constant repetitive action, for example, could be re-focused on something that creates or builds something. To put it another way, the behaviour can be adapted to something else.

Maladaptive behaviour, on the other hand, is a type of behaviour that is frequently used to reduce anxiety, but the end result is dysfunctional and non-productive. Avoiding situations, for example, may temporarily reduce your anxiety, but it is counterproductive in terms of addressing the underlying issue in the long run. Because its assessment is relatively free of subjectivity, maladaptive behaviour is frequently used as an indicator of abnormality or mental dysfunction. However, many moral behaviours, such as dissent or abstinence, can be harmful.

Adaptive behaviour reflects a person's social and practical ability to meet the demands of daily life.

Behavioural patterns evolve as a person grows, as do life settings and social constructs, personal values, and others' expectations. It is critical to assess adaptive behaviour in order to determine how well a person functions in daily life, including vocational, social, and educational functions [1].

Problems with assessing long-term and short-term adaptation

One issue with assessing adaptive behaviour is that what appears to be adaptive in the short run may be maladaptive in the long run, and vice versa. For example, in the case of a group with rules that insist on drinking harmful amounts of alcohol, both abstinence and moderate drinking (moderate as defined by actual health effects, not socially constructed rules) may appear maladaptive if assessments are strictly short term, but an assessment focusing on long-term survival would find that it was adaptive and that obedience to the drinking rule was maladaptive. Some researchers argue that there are such differences between short-term and long-term effects in the context of the harmful consequences of short-term compliance with destructive rules [2].

Adaptive behaviors in education

Adaptive behaviour in education is defined as behaviour that meets the needs of the community of stakeholders (parents, teachers, peers, and later employers) as well as the needs of the learner now and in the future. These behaviours include, for example, effective speech, self-help, money management, cooking, and reading [3].

Adaptive behaviour training is an essential component of any educational programme, but it is especially important for children with special needs. The US Department of Education has set aside billions of dollars for special education programmes aimed at improving educational and early intervention outcomes for disabled children. The National Research Council of the United States published a comprehensive review of interventions for children and adults with autism in 2001 [4].

Adaptive behaviour includes performing daily activities in a socially responsible and independent manner. However, the specific activities and skills required may vary depending on the setting. School and academic skills are adaptive when a student goes to school. However, some of those same skills may be ineffective or harmful in the workplace, so the transition from school to work requires careful considerations [5].

References

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Received: 04-May-2022, Manuscript No. AAJMHA-22-63725; Editor assigned: 06-May-2022, PreQC No. AAJMHA-22-63725(PQ); Reviewed: 20-May-2022, QC No. AAJMHA-22-63725; Revised: 24-May-2022, Manuscript No. AAJMHA-22-63725(R); Published: 27-May-2022, DOI:10.35841/ajmha-6.3.114